

Special Issue "Life Cycle Thinking and Sustainability Assessment of Buildings"

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A special issue of *Sustainability* (ISSN 2071-1050). This special issue belongs to the section "[Green Building](#)".

Deadline for manuscript submissions: **closed (31 December 2022)** | Viewed by 16326

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Special Issue Information

Dear Colleagues,

Sustainable development, climate change and other environmental problems are of high concern, as manifested in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Paris Agreement on Climate Change. Buildings are highly relevant in this regard as, most of the time, people are inside buildings and a large share of total energy use is connected to buildings' life cycle.

Wisely used, life cycle thinking can prevent burden shifting between life cycle stages and environmental, social and economic impacts in the different stages of a building's long cradle-to-grave/cradle-to-cradle life.

Up to now, the focus has rightly been on the use phase as buildings are long-lived products. Hence, the use phase, with its energy use, is often the dominating stage in a building or building elements impact assessment (Baldassarri et al. 2017, Lavagna et al. 2018). However, when buildings are built to near or nearly zero, zero and plus building standards, where energy in the use phase becomes respectively small, around zero or even negative (i.e. buildings that produce surplus energy), the environmental impact of the use phase might not be so dominating anymore (Paleari et al. 2016, Schau et al., forthcoming).

The goal of this Special Issue is to explore how state-of-the-art research and practice in life cycle thinking of the built environment is developing, along with improvements in building construction. Research related to the new construction and renovation of existing buildings, that takes into account a holistic, life cycle approach and several SDGs, is of interest. New construction, whole buildings and building elements, fossil fuel free and zero waste construction, are among the topics for this Special Issue. Case studies, comments, reviews and method papers, not only limited to LCA, but also social LCA and life costing, eventually integrated, or not, into a life cycle sustainability assessment (Finkbeiner, et al. 2010), are welcome.

Literature:

Baldassarri, C., Allacker, K., Reale, F., Castellani, V., & Sala, S. (2017). *Consumer Footprint: Basket of Products indicator on Housing*. EUR 28765 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg: <https://doi.org/10.2760/05316>

Finkbeiner, M., Schau, E. M., Lehmann, A., & Traverso, M. (2010). Towards life cycle sustainability assessment. *Sustainability*, 2(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su2103309>

Lavagna, M., Baldassarri, C., Campioli, A., Giorgi, S., Valle, A. D., Castellani, V., & Sala, S. (2018). Benchmarks for environmental impact of housing in Europe: Definition of archetypes and LCA of the residential building stock. *Building and Environment*, 145(August), 260–275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2018.09.008>

Paleari, M., Lavagna, M., & Campioli, A. (2016). The assessment of the relevance of building components and life phases for the environmental profile of nearly zero-energy buildings: life cycle assessment of a multifamily building in Italy. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 21(12), 1667–1690. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1133-6>

Schau EM, Prelovšek Niemelä E, Niemelä AJ, Alencar Gavric TA and Šušteršič I (forthcoming) *Life cycle assessment benchmark for wooden buildings in Europe* in Kłos Z, Kałkowska J, Kasprzak J (eds): *Towards Sustainable Future. Current Challenges and Prospects in the Life Cycle Management - LCM 2019*. Dordrecht: Springer

Dr. Erwin M. Schau
Ms. Eva Prelovšek Niemelä
Guest Editors

Manuscript Submission Information

Manuscripts should be submitted online at www.mdpi.com by **registering** and **logging in to this website**. Once you are registered, **click here to go to the submission form**. Manuscripts can be submitted until the deadline. All submissions that pass pre-check are peer-reviewed. Accepted papers will be published continuously in the journal (as soon as accepted) and will be listed together on the special issue website. Research articles, review articles as well as short communications are invited. For planned papers, a title and short abstract (about 100 words) can be sent to the Editorial Office for announcement on this website.

Submitted manuscripts should not have been published previously, nor be under consideration for publication elsewhere (except conference proceedings papers). All manuscripts are thoroughly refereed through a single-blind peer-review process. A guide for authors and other relevant information for submission of manuscripts is available on the [Instructions for Authors](#) page. *Sustainability* is an international peer-reviewed open access semimonthly journal published by MDPI.

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Keywords

- life cycle thinking (LCT)
- buildings
- building elements

- construction
- renovation
- life cycle assessment (LCA)
- social LCA (S-LCA)
- life cycle costing (LCC)
- sustainability assessment

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Research

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Modelling the Slovenian Wood Industry's Response to the Greenhouse Gas Paris Agreement and the EU "Fit for 55" Green Transition Plan

by

Erwin M. Schau

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Igor Gavrić

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Iztok Šušteršič

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Eva Prelovšek Niemelä

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Balázs Dávid

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Jaka Gašper Pečnik

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David B. DeVallance

and

Črtomir Tavzes

Sustainability **2023**, *15*(10), 8376; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15108376> - 22 May 2023

Cited by 1 | Viewed by 1103

Abstract

Almost 200 nations, including the European Union, have signed the Paris Agreement that aims to limit the temperature rise to 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels by reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. To meet this target, a significant decrease in GHG emissions by 2030 [...] [Read more.](#)

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Life Cycle Assessment of Advanced Building Components towards NZEBs

by
Despoina Antypa

,
Foteini Petrakli

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Anastasia Gkika

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Pamela Voigt

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Alexander Kahnt

Robert Böhm

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Jan Suchorzewski

,
Andreia Araújo

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Susana Sousa

and

Elias P. Koumoulos

Sustainability **2022**, *14*(23), 16218; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142316218> - 05 Dec 2022

Cited by 2 | Viewed by 1194

Abstract

The building sector accounts for 40% of the total energy consumed in Europe at annual basis, together with the relevant Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions. In order to mitigate these impacts, the concept and establishment of the Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEBs) is under [...] [Read more.](#)

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Open Access **Editor's Choice** **Article**

A Temporal Perspective in Eco² Building Design

by

Patricia Schneider-Marin

and

Werner Lang

Sustainability **2022**, *14*(10), 6025; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14106025> - 16 May 2022

Cited by 3 | Viewed by 1260

Abstract

The architecture, engineering and construction (AEC) sector has great potential and responsibility for reducing its considerable resource consumption and high share of global emissions. However, economic factors are often cited as barriers to more environmentally friendly solutions in building design. Hence, environmental and [...] [Read more.](#)

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Open Access **Editor's Choice** **Article**

Integrating Environmental and Economic Perspectives in Building Design

by

Patricia Schneider-Marin

,

Anne Winkelkotte

and

Werner Lang

Sustainability **2022**, *14*(8), 4637; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084637> - 13 Apr 2022

Cited by 6 | Viewed by 1798

Abstract

With increasing environmental damage and decreasing resource availability, sustainability assessment in the building sector is gaining momentum. A literature review shows that the related methods for environmental and economic performance, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC), show great potential for [\[...\]](#)
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Implementing Artificial Intelligence Techniques to Predict Environmental Impacts: Case of Construction Products

by

Anish Koyamparambath

,

Naeem Adibi

,

Carolina Szablewski

,

Sierra A. Adibi

and

Guido Sonnemann

Sustainability **2022**, *14*(6), 3699; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14063699> - 21 Mar 2022

[Cited by 6](#) | Viewed by 4678

Abstract

Nowadays, product designers, manufacturers, and consumers consider the environmental impacts of products, processes, and services in their decision-making process. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a tool that assesses the environmental impacts over a product's life cycle. Conducting a life cycle assessment (LCA) requires [\[...\]](#)
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Implementation of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) in the Procurement Process of Buildings: A Systematic Literature Review

by

Marco Scherz

,

Antonija Ana Wieser

,

Alexander Passer

and

Helmuth Kreiner

Sustainability **2022**, *14*(24), 16967; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416967> - 18 Dec 2022

[Cited by 4](#) | Viewed by 1663

Abstract

The construction industry adds a high share to global CO₂ emissions and, thus, to the global climate crisis. Future buildings need to be planned, constructed, operated, and deconstructed in a lifecycle-oriented manner so that the building stock represents a capital asset for [\[...\]](#)
[Read more.](#)

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[Open Access](#)[Review](#)

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) in Earth Construction: A Systematic Literature Review Considering Five Construction Techniques

by

Deborah Arduin

Lucas Rosse Caldas

Rayane de Lima Moura Paiva

and

Fernando Rocha

Sustainability **2022**, *14*(20), 13228; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142013228> - 14 Oct 2022

Cited by 5 | Viewed by 2573

Abstract

In the past decade, there has been an increase in the environmental performance assessment in earth construction through the life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology. A Systematic Literature Review verified LCA methodology trends of five earth construction techniques from 2016 to April 2022, resulting [\[...\] Read more.](#) (This article belongs to the Special Issue [Life Cycle Thinking and Sustainability Assessment of Buildings](#))

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